

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of *Ischaemum Pilosum* (Klein.Ex Willd.) Wt

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Abstract

Ischaemum pilosum (Klein.ex Willd.) Wt belonging to the Poaceae Family locally known as “Kunda” commonly distributed in crops as a weed. Many medicinal uses have been reported in literature for this plant with much folk information. Preliminary phyto-chemical test for secondary metabolites has been done to extracted leaves powder in different solvent by standard protocols to detect the presence of Alkaloids, Phenols, Terperns, fatty acids etc. Proximate analysis and UV has been done as per well referenced protocols on the leaf extract of *Ischaemum pilosum*. The results revels very positive significance data from all phytochemical analysis, proximate analysis and for UV Visible spectral peaks. No such record for this plant has been reported erlier hance work will contribute farther more to evaluate functional thorpatic from plant.

Key Words: *Ischaemum pilosum*, *Phytochemistry*, *Secondary Metabolites*, *UV*, *Proximate analysis*).

Introduction

Ischaemum pilosum belonging to the family Poaceae, locally name as *Kunda*, *Kons* and *Khavon*. It is a typical type of Perennial creeping grass with the stolons that covers shoots at the base with dry striate leaf sheaths. Stems 60-90 cm stout. Leaves long, narrow, convolute; ligules

membranous. Spike 2-6 on the stout peduncle. Spikelets wooly white and troublesome weed on black cotton soil.

Ischaemum pilosum Klein ex Willd were chosen as sources of lignocellulosic material for the preparation of ethanol (Soe Soe Than 2016). A decoction of root powder is given against urine stone twice in a day for seven days. A teaspoon of root powder is given to cow, twice in a day for 5 days to flow milk (Rothe *et.al.*, 2017)

Materials and Methods

The present investigation i.e., pharmacognostical, Phytochemical and sedative activity of leaves of *Ischaemum pilosum* is proposed since no such comprehensive work is available specially for Phytochemical work .

Field Work: *Ischaemum pilosum* (Klein.ex Willd.) Wt plant were collected from the forests of Toranmal of Shahda Tahsil of Nandurbar Disterct. With collection ethonobotanical importances also been recoreded from local tribal peoples laeeter cross the collected information data with existng literature of ethnomedicn. Plant sample were collected for lab work and also recoreded the geographical location of plant for reviste in feutre.

Laboratory work: Taxonomical identification was done with the help different flora like Flora of Presidency of Bombay, Flora of Dhule and Nandurbar District and recorded taxonomical characters.

Proximate Analysis: It was taken for identification for moisture, Dry matter and Ash content.

Moisture content: The moisture of the sample was lost by volatilization caused by heat. Moisture of the material was determined by following the method by AOAC (Association of Official Analytical Chemists) 1990. Dishes were washed with detergents and then were dried at 105 0 C in oven for overnight. Then dishes were removed from oven and then kept in dessicator for cooling and weights. The estimation was done in triplicate and the mean values of both were recorded to calculate the moisture content using the following relationship.

2 gm sample was taken in dishes and placed in oven at 105 0 C overnight. The moisture was calculated by using the following formulae:-

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Weight of fresh sample} - \text{Weight of dry sample})}{\text{Weight of fresh sample}} \times 100$$

Dry matter Content: The dry matter of the sample represents the amount of material left after the complete removal of moisture from it. Dry matter of the sample were determined by following the method by AOAC (Association of Official Analytical Chemists) 1990. Dishes were washed with detergents and then were dried at 105 0 C in oven for overnight. Then dishes were removed from oven and then kept in dessicator for cooling and weights. The estimation was done in triplicate and the mean values of both were recorded to calculate the dry matter Content.

2 gm sample was taken in dishes and placed in oven at 105 0 C overnight. The moisture was calculated by using the following formulae:-

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Dry matter (\%)} \\ = \frac{(\text{Weight of dish} + \text{Weight of dried sample}) - \text{Weight of dish}}{\text{Weight of sample before drying}} \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

Ash Content: Ash value was determined by following the method of AOAC (1990). For this crucible were kept in a muffle furnace at 600 0 C for 1h. Then they were transferred crucible from furnace to a desiccator and cooled to room temperature and weighed as quickly as possible to prevent moisture absorption. Two gram dry plant part sample was taken in tared silica crucible and placed in a muffle furnace at 600 0 C for 6h. Then crucible was transferred to a desiccator and cooled to room temperature, crucible was transferred as quickly as possible to avoid moisture absorption. The percentage of ash was calculated by using the following formula:-

$$\text{Ash (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Phytochemical studies:

	<i>Name of the test</i>	<i>Procedure</i>	<i>Observation</i>	<i>References</i>
1	Alkaloids	0.5ml extract + treated with few drops of 1ml 2N Hcl +Mayer's reagent / Dragandorf reagent Hager's reagent	Orange precipitate Orange color White ppt. Yellow ppt.	Vaishali <i>et al.</i> 2013
2	Anthraquinone	Few drops of extract was boiled with 10% Hcl for few minutes & cool + CHCl ₃ (Chloroform)to filtrate & few drops of NH ₃ added and heated	Rose pink color	Yusuf et al. 2014
3	Cardiac glycosides	0.5ml extract + 1ml water + aqueous solution NaoH some drops for color	Brown interface, violet ring below and greenish ring at lowest part	Vaishali <i>et al.</i> 2013 Kangogo et al. 2014
4	Coumarins	2 ml of extract, 3 ml of 10% naoh	Appearance of yellow colour indicates presence of coumarins.	Dharmendra et al. 2012
5	Flavonoids	0.5ml extract + 5-10 drops of dilute Hcl + small amount / pieces + then boiled for few min. Shinodaw's Test Zn-HCl acid reduction Test	Red color Magenta color	Krishnaiah et al. 2007 Dharmendra et al. 2012 Yusuf et al. 2014
6	Glycosides	Anthrone + H ₂ SO ₄ + Heat	Purple or green	Dharmendra et al. 2012 Yusuf et al. 2014
7	Phenols	Fecl ₃ Sample + lead acetate + water	Intense color Formation of white ppt	Dharmendra et al. 2012 Yusuf et al. 2014 Kangogo et al. 2014
8	Reducing sugars	0.5ml extract was dissolved in 5ml of water and filter it + boiled with Fehling's solution A & B for few min.	Orange red precipitate positively detects reducing sugars.	Yusuf et al. 2014
9	Saponins	Sample + water + shaking	Formation of honey	Dharmendra et al.

			comb like froth Presence of froths/foams	2012 Yusuf et al. 2014 Kangogo et al. 2014
10	Steroids	Salkowski's test and Liebermann burchard's test	Dark green color in the upper layer and red color in the lower layer indicating the presence of steroids	Dharmendra et al. 2012 Vaishali <i>et al.</i> 2013 Yusuf et al. 2014
11	Tannin	0.5ml of aqueous extract + 10% lead acetate few drops	Greenish-black colouration	Vaishali <i>et al.</i> 2013 Yusuf et al. 2014 Mohammad et al. 2014
12	Triterpenes	Liebermann Test Salkowski Test Noller's test	Bluish green Red & fluorescent Pink color OR Reddish-brown coloration of the interface	Vaishali <i>et al.</i> 2013 Yusuf et al. 2014 Kangogo et al. 2014

UV Visible Spectral Analysis: Extraction of dry leaves was carried out for 5 g of powder for 24 cycle of soxhlet extract. Three solvent were used for extraction viz. Methanol, Ethanol and Chloroform. Different concentrations and dilutions were made for UV analysis in 300nm to 1000nm range for all three samples in replicate.

Concentration	Methanol Extract	Ethanol Extract	Chloroform Extract
20%	200µl/ml	200µl/ml	200µl/ml
40%	400 µl/ml	400 µl/ml	400 µl/ml
60%	600 µl/ml	600 µl/ml	600 µl/ml
80%	800 µl/ml	800 µl/ml	800 µl/ml
100%	Pure extract	Pure extract	Pure extract

Result and Discussions

Proximate Analysis:

Plant Part Used	Moisture content	Dry matter Content	Ash Content
Leaves (w/w)	51.00 %	49.00 %	12.00%
Stem Parts (w/w)	54.00 %	46.50%	14.00%
Root (w/w)	51.50 %	46.50%	15.50%
Total	52.16%	47.33%	30.33%

Primary Phytochemistry:

Sr. No.	Phyto-constituents	<i>Ischaemum pilosum</i> (Willd.) Wight.											
		SHOOT POWDER						ROOT POWDER					
		Aq	M	E	Et	C	A	Aq	M	E	Et	C	A
1	Alkaloids	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+
2	Anthraquinone	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
3	Cardiac glycosides	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
4	Coumarins	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+
5	Flavonoids	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
6	Glycosides	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-
7	Phenols	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+
8	Reducing sugars	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-
9	Saponins	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-

10	Steroids	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+
11	Tannin	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
12	Triterpenes	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
Aq= Aqueous, M= Methanol, E= Ethanol, Et=Petroleum Ether, C= Chloroform, A=Acetone													

UV Visible Spectral Analysis:

(a)

(b)

(a) Leaves Extract (b) Root Extract
UV Spectral Analysis of *I pilosum*
(60% conc. Ethanol Extract)

(a)

(b)

(a) Leaves Extract (b) Root Extract
UV Spectral Analysis of *I pilosum*
(60% conc. Chloroform Extract)

Conclusions

The current work from the survey and field observation its find that there is very significance medicinal important of *Catunaregum spinosa* among tribes. As wel as it has been found that iit has been used for multiple purpose in different area like fruit has an abortifficient activity (Agrawal *et al.*, 1999), bark used for diarrhoea and dysentery (Chopra, *et al.*, 1956), sometime root bark past also important in rheumatism, relieve pain of bruises and bone aches during fevers and to disperse abscesses (Dastur *et al.*, 1962).

Lab and experimental reveals that Moisture content of Leaves (w/w), Stem Bark (w/w) and Root Bark (w/w) are 87.50%, 4600% and 59.50% respectively. Dry matter content of Leaves (w/w), Stem Bark (w/w) and Root Bark (w/w) are 12.50%, 5400% and 40.50% respectively. Ash content of Leaves (w/w), Stem Bark (w/w) and Root Bark (w/w) are 09.50%, 17.50% and 13.50% respectively.

For another Parameter in phytochemical test for different primary and secondary metabolites it find that different solvent are effected the positive of result. For leaves, Stem Bark and Root Bark sample it was found that except Anthraquinone, Coumarins and Steroids were not detected among all parameters in six different solvent.

UV Visible analysis graphical representation recorded between 300:1000 nm shows sharp peak in Leaf sample in 400 µl/ml of different extract.

Acknowledgments

Authors would like to acknowledge their thanks for the support and guidance of Dr. S Gosavi Sir Taloda College, Mr. Javed Sir, M. J College, to Principal Dr. Deore sir Jijamata college, NUM Jalgaon, UGC for financial support and lastly but not least to all our researchers of lab.

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